

MultiXscale

Training Activity Technical Support Infrastructure

MultiXscale Deliverable 6.2
Deliverable Type: Report
Delivered in December, 2024

MultiXscale
EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for
Multiscale Modelling

Co-funded by
the European Union

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

Acknowledgement

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101093169.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project and Deliverable Information

Project Title Project Ref. Project Website EuroHPC Project Officer	MultiXscale: EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for Multiscale Modelling Grant Agreement 101093169 https://www.multixscale.eu Dr. Matteo Mascagni
Deliverable ID Deliverable Nature Dissemination Level Contractual Date of Delivery Actual Date of Delivery	D6.2 Report Public Project Month 24 (31 st December, 2024) 30 th December, 2024
Description of Deliverable	Report outlining the technical infrastructure created, maintained and used to support the training activities of the project.

Document Control Information

Document	Title:	Training Activity Technical Support Infrastructure
	ID:	D6.2
	Version:	As of December, 2024
	Status:	Accepted by SC
	Available at: Document history:	https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables Internal Project Management Link
Review	Review Status:	Reviewed
Authorship	Written by:	Thomas Röblitz (University of Bergen)
	Contributors:	Alan O'Cais (University of Barcelona)
	Reviewed by: Approved by:	Elisabeth Ortega (HPCNow!) Alan O'Cais (UB)

Document Keywords

Keywords:	MultiXscale, HPC, software, training, infrastructure
-----------	--

30th December, 2024

Disclaimer: This deliverable has been prepared by the responsible Work Package of the Project in accordance with the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement. It solely reflects the opinion of the parties to such agreements on a collective basis in the context of the Project and to the extent foreseen in such agreements.

Copyright notices: This deliverable was co-ordinated by Thomas Röblitz¹ (University of Bergen) on behalf of the MultiXscale consortium with contributions from Alan O'Cais (University of Barcelona). This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit:

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

¹thomas.roblitz@uib.no

Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	2
1.1 Target audience	2
1.2 Deliverable outline	2
1.3 Partner contributions	2
2 Magic Castle	3
2.1 General configuration	3
2.1.1 Infrastructure configuration	4
2.1.2 Puppet	4
2.2 Auto-scaling	4
2.3 Hardware support	5
2.4 Resource providers	5
3 Lhumos Training Portal	6
3.1 Design and maintenance	6
3.2 Features developed	6
3.3 Towards a production-quality service	7
4 CASTIEL2 training collaborations	8
4.1 Ambassador Program	8
4.2 HPC in Europe training calendar	8
5 Conclusion and outlook	9
References	10

List of Figures

1 Terraform variables stored in Terraform Cloud	5
---	---

Executive Summary

This report details the key technology infrastructures created, configured, used and maintained by MultiXscale to support its training activities.

Magic Castle is an open-source software infrastructure designed to replicate High Performance Computing (HPC) environments using cloud resources, which can be deployed quickly. For MultiXscale, Magic Castle is used to set up multi-architecture Slurm clusters in cloud environments, with the software stack provided by EESSI. It uses Terraform to provision the hardware, and Puppet to configure the hardware as a Slurm cluster and ensure it operates as intended.

Given the heavy adoption of Magic Castle within the project for training purposes and beyond, it is well supported among the consortium with excellent dialogue with the lead developer. It supports ARM and x86_64 CPUs, and also has support for NVIDIA GPUs.

Lhumos is a web portal for educational content on modeling and simulation. Originally developed within the E-CAM project, it is now co-developed and maintained by MultiXscale and CECAM, leveraging the [Clowder framework](#) for data storage and metadata generation. CECAM maintains the user-facing front-end of Lhumos, while MultiXscale manages the Clowder back-end infrastructure, including data storage, metadata extractors, and the use of Terraform for hardware provisioning (with resources currently provided by [CSCS](#)). Docker Compose orchestrates services, with custom extractor utilities stored in the Lhumos GitHub repository.

Extraction support for YouTube, GitHub, and GitLab URLs to enable real-time metadata retrieval via API calls was added to Lhumos. Advanced image formats and OpenCV3 integration for better presentation and PDF handling, including slide previews and compression were also added. These features allow for an enriched user experience in the Lhumos front-end.

Lhumos is on track for a robust formal launch, integrating modern technologies and enhanced metadata capabilities for improved user engagement. The transition to a production-quality service, with Lhumos and Clowder v2 is scheduled for early 2025. There will be a migration from OpenStack to Kubernetes at CSCS for Clowder v2 provisioning, with [Cineca](#) providing temporary support and a failover/backup site. Both Cineca and CSCS will be used to maintain the infrastructure long-term to ensure reliability.

The MultiXscale Ambassador program, connected to CASTIEL2, began hosting events during the second reporting period. It operates with minimal technical infrastructure, supported by a mailing list that announces training events and allows Ambassadors to sign up, promote events locally, and organize hybrid workshops. These workshops use Zoom for instruction, incorporating breakout rooms for hands-on support with Ambassadors, while maintaining attendee privacy by recording only the main sessions. This approach has been positively received by CASTIEL2, with several National Competence Center (NCC) representatives joining the initiative.

Additionally, CASTIEL2 requires all Center of Excellence (CoE) training events to be listed on the HPC in Europe portal. Tools originally developed during the FocusCoE project, including a registration form, metadata extractor, and a JavaScript library, facilitate the integration of event data into websites. Maintained on GitLab, these tools have undergone updates to align with the portal's API changes and now include features such as direct links to project-specific event histories. While the CASTIEL2 Information Sharing System (C2ISS) will eventually replace or update this service, the tool currently remains critical for managing training event metadata for CASTIEL2 and MultiXscale.

1 Introduction

This report details the key technology infrastructures created, configured, used and maintained by MultiXscale to support its training activities.

1.1 Target audience

The report is intended to provide an overview of the technical infrastructure of the MultiXscale project, and is primarily intended for the project monitors. For a wider audience, it provides an outline of how these tools are used and developed by MultiXscale in the project context.

1.2 Deliverable outline

Section 2 outlines the configuration and project usage of Magic Castle, designed to quickly replicate HPC environments using cloud resources. It is used to create ephemeral clusters to support MultiXscale training events.

Section 3 provides information on the role of MultiXscale in the maintenance and development of the Lhumos training portal. The portal is used to archive the training content provided by MultiXscale.

Section 4 outlines the technical underpinning of the MultiXscale Ambassador program, and the training event scraping tool that is maintained by MultiXscale. Both of these relate to joint activities with CASTIEL2.

1.3 Partner contributions

This report is connected to Task 6.2 of MultiXscale:

Create the technical and organisational infrastructure to support the training and education program.

- The technical infrastructure will be composed of on-demand cloud-based resources for training events (including fast interconnect and accelerator capabilities), and a custom training portal to host recordings of training events and other related material. Necessary technical development of the tools to support these is included in this task.
- The organisational infrastructure will be the creation of an "Ambassador program" for representatives of CECAM nodes and HPC National Competence Centres. Yearly coordination events for the Ambassador program (train-the-trainer type events) will be held from the second year of the project.

Contributions to this task come from partners UB (with a 5PM budget) and UiB (with a 2PM budget).

2 Magic Castle

The most elaborate technical infrastructure used for training is [Magic Castle](#). As described in [1]:

[Magic Castle](#) is an open-source software that replicates the HPC infrastructure experience via community or commercial cloud resources. It is easy to deploy and can be created in minutes. Once their cluster is deployed, the user is provided with a complete HPC cluster software environment including the scheduler, a data-transfer node, JupyterHub, and thousands of software applications compiled by experts and accessible via CernVM-FS. Since its initial public release in 2018, Magic Castle has been used for thousands of workshops and tutorials world-wide.

For MultiXscale, Magic Castle has been shown to be mature enough to use as the tool of choice to support multi-architecture Slurm clusters in public/commercial cloud environments. Such clusters are currently being used to provide resources for the building of software for the European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI). Given this, the utilisation of Magic Castle for training purposes is, to a significant extent, a simpler use case.

Here we discuss basic configuration for our use case, [detailed documentation is available in the Magic Castle GitHub repository](#).

2.1 General configuration

The main configuration for a Magic Castle cluster is contained in a single file, `main.tf`. The most critical configuration done by the end user is in a module corresponding to the resource provider, see Listing 1 for an example for Azure.

```

1 module "azure" {
2   source           = "./azure"
3   config_git_url  = "https://github.com/ComputeCanada/puppet-magic_castle.git"
4   config_version = "14.1.2"
5
6   cluster_name = "azure-alma94-2411-mc-14"
7   domain       = "eessi.io"
8
9   # Using the AZure CLI, you can list the image versions that are available to use. For example,
10  # az vm image list --location eastus --publisher almalinux --offer almalinux-x86_64 --sku 9-gen2 --all
11  # az vm image list --location eastus --publisher almalinux --offer almalinux-arm --sku 9-arm-gen2 --all
12  # (Note: available versions may be location specific!)
13  image = { publisher = "almalinux", offer = "almalinux-x86_64", sku = "9-gen2", version = "9.4.2024080501" }
14
15  instances = {
16    mgmt = { type = "Standard_DS3_v2", disk_size = 60, count = 1, tags = ["mgmt", "puppet", "nfs"] },
17    login = { type = "Standard_DS5_v2", disk_size = 60, count = 1, tags = ["login", "public", "proxy"] },
18    x86-64-amd-zen4-node = { type = "Standard_HB176-24rs_v4", disk_size = 50, count = 2, tags = ["node", "pool"] },
19    aarch64-neoverse-n1-node = { type = "Standard_D16ps_v5", disk_size = 50, count = 1, tags = ["node", "pool"] },
20    image = { publisher = "almalinux", offer = "almalinux-arm", sku = "9-arm-gen2", version = "9.4.2024080501" }
21  }
22
23  # var.pool is managed by Slurm through Terraform REST API.
24  # To let Slurm manage a type of nodes, add "pool" to its tag list.
25  # Refer to Magic Castle Documentation - Enable Magic Castle Autoscaling
26  pool = var.pool
27
28  volumes = { nfs = { home = { size = 100 }, project = { size = 3500 }, scratch = { size = 50 } } }
29
30  # SSH pubkeys that can access 'centos' account which has sudo rights
31  public_keys = []
32
33  nb_users = 0
34  # Shared password, randomly chosen if blank
35  guest_passwd = ""
36
37  eyaml_key = base64decode(var.tfc_eyaml_key)
38  hieradata = file("data.yaml")
39
40  # Azure specifics
41  location = "eastus"
42
43  # use the EESSI software stack
44  software_stack = "eessi"

```

Listing 1: Core `main.tf` configuration for an Azure multi-architecture cluster

2.1.1 Infrastructure configuration

The main infrastructure items that an end user decides are the instances type and number, and the volumes to be used to support the shared file system(s).

For instances, the user defines the type (for example, in Azure the instance type `Standard_HB176-24rs_v4` corresponds to a Zen 4 node), the `disk_size`, the count (how many there should be), and the image (if not using the default image, required when one mixes architectures). The tags indicate to Puppet (see Section 2.1.2) what functions the instance has.

For volumes, the user provides the type (`nfs`), and the mount points and sizes.

2.1.2 Puppet

Puppet is a widely used open-source configuration management tool that automates the process of configuring, managing, and deploying software and systems across large-scale IT environments. Puppet uses declarative programming, meaning the user defines the desired state of the machines being managed. It has a client/server architecture: the clients contact the server to query their required state and then implement the changes necessary to get themselves to that state.

This approach is very useful for Magic Castle, as it largely removes the need to have active system administration of the system since the Puppet client tries to do this automatically. The configuration of the cluster is done by **Puppet Magic Castle** which is what configures the provisioned hardware with all the services.

In Listing 1, which Puppet configuration to use is given by `config_git_url`, with the version provided by `config_version`. **Puppet Magic Castle** can be customised extensively. This can be done directly in the `main.tf` file for some items (such as `software_stack = "eessi"`), or at a much more detailed level via a `data.yaml` file as in Listing 2.

```

1 ---
2 # Slurm configuration
3 profile::slurm::base::slurm_version: '24.05'
4 profile::slurm::controller::tfe_token: "ENC[PKCS7,EXAMPLE=="
5 profile::slurm::controller::tfe_workspace: "ws-EXAMPLE"
6 # Default users
7 profile::users::ldap::users:
8   user1:
9     groups: ['def-users']
10    public_keys: ['ssh-ed25519 AAAAC3n1ktWwemcK5 user1@email.me']
11    manage_password: false
12 # limit squid cache size on management machine
13 profile::squid::server::cache_size: 2048
14 # additional packages
15 profile::base::packages:
16 - aptainer
17 - screen

```

Listing 2: Customising Puppet modules

In Listing 2, we show how to specify

- a specific Slurm version being used and the settings needed by Slurm to talk to Terraform Cloud (see Section 2.2),
- the `user1` is automatically added to the cluster,
- the size of the Squid cache used by CernVM-FS is limited,
- additional OS packages have been added to the default configuration.

2.2 Auto-scaling

Clusters created by Magic Castle can have dynamic resources, meaning that some infrastructure is only provisioned on demand. This has obvious cost and energy benefits when resources are only sporadically used, such as is typically the case for a training course.

For autoscaling to work, it requires interplay between Magic Castle (which uses Terraform) and Puppet Magic Castle. For Terraform, this is done by defining two variables, as in Listing 3.

```

1 variable "pool" {
2   description = "Slurm pool of compute nodes"
3   default = []
4 }
5
6 # This variable is the cluster private key and provided via Terraform Cloud
7 # (see https://github.com/ComputeCanada/magic_castle/tree/main/docs#415-eyaml_key-optional)
8 variable "tfc_eyaml_key" {}

```

Listing 3: Terraform Cloud variables in main.tf configuration

Terraform is actually executed in Terraform Cloud (which has an API), and the values of these variables are set there, see Fig. 1. Critically in the case of pool, the value can be modified via the correct API call, and the modification can trigger a new Terraform run. This behaviour is what allows for the dynamic scaling capabilities of the cluster: the Slurm cluster power saving features are used to trigger an API call for the pool variable which in turn causes a node instance to start or stop.

Workspace variables (2)
Variables defined within a workspace always overwrite variables from variable sets that have the same type and the same key. Learn more about variable set [precedence](#).

Key	Value	Category	Actions
pool HCL	[]	terraform	<input type="button" value="..."/>
tfc_eyaml_key	LS0tLS1CRUdJTiBQUkVhdGVudQk1JSUUV2UUIICURBTKna3Foa2IH0XcwQkFRRUZBQVNDQktjd2dnU2pBZ0V0BQW9JQkFRQzh1OTdY	terraform	<input type="button" value="..."/>

Figure 1: Terraform variables stored in Terraform Cloud

For Slurm to have the correct permissions to make the API call, Puppet Magic Castle needs information to allow it make an authenticated API call to Terraform Cloud. This information is provided in an encrypted format in data.yaml:

```

1 profile::slurm::controller::tfe_token: "ENC[PKCS7,EXAMPLE=="
2 profile::slurm::controller::tfe_workspace: "ws-EXAMPLE"

```

Listing 4: API authentication information for Terraform Cloud

2.3 Hardware support

Magic Castle supports x86_64 and aarch64 CPUs. In addition, it automatically detects and configures NVIDIA GPUs. As of December 2024, this set covers the entire spectrum of software provided by software.eessi.io within EESSI (with EESSI providing the hardware optimised software stack).

With respect to the HPC interconnects, Magic Castle currently relies on the underlying image for hardware support. Fabric support for AWS EFA and Infiniband has been shown to work for EESSI within a Magic Castle context.

2.4 Resource providers

EESSI and MultiXscale currently receive cloud resource support from 4 locations (directly and indirectly):

- Provider AWS,
- Provider Azure,
- Provider OpenStack (via the ACCESS program in the US, and at Jülich Supercomputing Centre).

3 Lhumos Training Portal

As introduced in [1],

The Learning Hub For Modelling and Simulation (Lhumos) is a web portal for educational material for modelling and simulation. It is being co-developed by MultiXscale, after being designed, conceived, and implemented within the MultiXscale predecessor E-CAM.

...

Since E-CAM, the original Clowder instance is now being given a far more user-friendly interface by Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire (CECAM), called Lhumos, while still retaining the original Clowder framework for data storage and metadata generation.

MultiXscale is concerned with the data storage and metadata generation via Clowder for Lhumos.

3.1 Design and maintenance

The user-facing front-end of Lhumos is now maintained by CECAM. MultiXscale maintains the Clowder infrastructure back-end to store data, as well as the associated *extractors* to create metadata around the stored data.

Terraform is again used to configure the hardware resources to support Lhumos (which are currently provided by CSCS), and the Terraform code is stored in a [Lhumos GitHub repository](#).

[Docker Compose](#) is used for orchestration of all the services that make up Clowder. Most of the required Docker images come from Clowder, but the custom extractor definition files are stored in the [extractors subfolder of the Lhumos repository](#). It is the extractors that are the primary maintenance effort for the Clowder back-end as their feature-set has been extended and they may require updating as the Clowder version is kept up-to-date.

The maintenance history of this Clowder infrastructure can be viewed by browsing the [commit history of the Lhumos GitHub repository](#).

There have been two failures of the infrastructure at CSCS, which required rebuilding the Clowder service. However, the Terraform and Docker Compose approach means that this can be done in a matter of hours. The primary data object for the service is the Mongo database, which is backed up at CSCS. If the Mongo database is available, the service can be quickly reconstructed.

3.2 Features developed

Within MultiXscale, a number of additional features have been added to the extractor services:

- Support for metadata extraction for YouTube videos. A URL based extraction that gathers the critical information related to a YouTube video, in particular its identifier in YouTube. This allows the front-end to make direct API calls to YouTube to gather realtime metadata about the video. An example of the metadata is:

```
clowder_git_repo: false
clowder_youtube_video_id: Fzv4iei1ljo
X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN
tls: true
clowder_page_title: Making scientific software EESSI - and fast - YouTube
clowder_preview_image: 64a291e1e4b0fdae771569f8
```

- Support for metadata extraction for GitHub repositories. A URL based extraction to gather metadata about a URL connected to a GitHub repository. Provides the API url for the repository so that the front-end can make a direct API call to GitHub to gather realtime metadata about the repository. An example of the metadata is:

```
clowder_git_repo: true
clowder_git_type: github
clowder_git_api_url: https://api.github.com/repos/easybuilders/easybuild-framework
clowder_page_title: Allow use of alternate envvar(s) to $HOME for user modules
clowder_preview_image: 649ebb60e4b0fdae77152915
```

- Support for metadata extraction for GitLab repositories. A URL based extraction to gather metadata about a URL connected to a GitLab repository. Provides the API url for the repository so that the front-end can make a direct API call to GitLab to gather realtime metadata about the repository. Works with [gitlab.com](#) and also

private GitLab instances. An example of the metadata is:

```
clowder_git_repo: true
clowder_git_type: gitlab
clowder_git_api_url: https://gitlab.com/api/v4/projects/991013
clowder_page_title: Gentoo Linux / Gentoo Portage tree
clowder_preview_image: 6548ee97e4b03747e0add9ed
```

- Next generation image formats for images created by the presentation extractor, these allow for better compression of slides extracted from presentations.
- Support for OpenCV3 in presentation extractor. Computer vision is used to identify slide transitions, supporting OpenCV3 allows for the use of the most recent algorithms for this use case.
- Preview slides for PDF documents, so that image previews of PDF pages can be provided to the front-end.
- PDF compression of large PDF documents. Since PDF documents are rendered directly in the front-end, large PDF documents can be problematic as they are likely to be slow to load. Compression allows for the creation of size-limited PDF documents (however, potentially with a loss of quality).

All of these items are created in order to provide the additional metadata necessary to create a richer user experience in the Lhumos front-end.

3.3 Towards a production-quality service

Lhumos is currently in beta status, with a formal release scheduled for Q1 2025. Clowder v2 is currently also in beta, with an expected release also in early 2025. In addition, CSCS will no longer maintain an OpenStack instance, moving to a Kubernetes platform instead. Together, this implies that 2025 is a good time to transition to use Kubernetes to provision the Clowder v2 services.

For the transition from Clowder v1 to v2, we will temporarily transfer the infrastructure to the Openstack service of Cineca to maintain the service while we prepare Clowder v2 via Kubernetes at CSCS.

Going forward, both sites (Cineca and CSCS) will be maintained, with one acting as backup and failover for the other.

4 CASTIEL2 training collaborations

Several training-related initiatives within MultiXscale are connected to collaborative activities with CASTIEL2.

4.1 Ambassador Program

The Ambassador program of MultiXscale (introduced in [1]) began to have its first events in the second reporting period. While there is no extensive technical infrastructure needed to support this program, there are nevertheless two items worthy of note:

- An Ambassador program mailing list has been created (Ambassador-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si). Each training event that is appropriate for an ambassador will be announced on the mailing list, and ambassadors who wish to sign up to support the event may do so. Ambassadors can advertise the event among their local users, and organise a "local" group that they will support during the event itself. The core idea is to enable a hybrid mode of workshop, with remote instruction and local support for groups of users.
- Instruction is provided via Zoom. The breakout room feature is used for hands-on components of workshops, with Ambassadors providing the support within their own breakout room. The instruction is recorded, and to preserve privacy attendees are not recommended to interact with the instructor directly there, but rather use online methods (such as Slack) to ask questions, or to ask their question via the Ambassador (who agrees in advance to be recorded). Breakout rooms are not recorded, and attendees can speak freely there.

This concept for Ambassadors has been presented to the CASTIEL2 consortium during the "Training Coffee Break" meetings of CASTIEL2. It has been very well received by the NCCs, and a number of NCC representatives have signed up to the program.

4.2 HPC in Europe training calendar

CASTIEL2 has requested that all CoE training events are added to the [High-Performance Computing in Europe portal](#). During the [FocusCoE](#) CSA project, Alan O'Cais developed the form to register these training events, a tool to extract/scrape the event metadata, and a javascript library to allow the injection of the scraped event data into partner sites. These tools are used by [CASTIEL2 and the NCCs](#), as well as [by MultiXscale itself](#) to present training events to those visiting their websites.

These [training calendar tools are hosted on GitLab](#) and continue to be maintained by Alan O'Cais, with some additional features being added. Maintenance is generally low, but upgrades in the HPC in Europe portal required updates to the event scraper to reflect new API endpoints. The primary added feature included directly linking to project-specific event histories in the portal (e.g., the [MultiXscale event history](#)).

Though this service will be replaced (or require significant updating) when the CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System (C2ISS) comes online, currently it remains the only way for CoEs (and others) to easily access the training event metadata collected via the portal.

5 Conclusion and outlook

The technical tools used to support the training activities of MultiXscale are well established at this point. Given this status, the primary concern going forward is the maintenance of existing services.

The most complex tool, Magic Castle, is heavily used within the project both for training purposes and also to support the build infrastructure of EESSI. Therefore, experience with this tool is spread among the team, and the interaction with the main developer is extremely good (to the point where Alan O’Cais traveled to [SC23 to co-present a tutorial on Magic Castle with the lead developer](#)). The lead developer is extremely responsive, and any issues are usually collaboratively remedied within a matter of days.

Lhumos will require additional attention in 2025 as it moves to a full production status, including transitioning the hosting infrastructure to Kubernetes, and upgrading the underlying data management infrastructure (Clowder). While this effort is relatively significant, it is a one-time only effort to place the service in a production quality status.

Other tools within the project are unlikely to require a significant maintenance going forward, and the focus will purely be on the utilisation of these tools for their intended purpose.

References

Acronyms used

EESSI European Environment for Scientific Software Installations

HPC High Performance Computing

CECAM Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire

CoE Center of Excellence

JSC Jülich Supercomputing Centre

NCC National Competence Center

Software mentioned

Lhumos Learning Hub For Modelling and Simulation

URLs referenced

Page ii

<https://www.multixscale.eu> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu>

<https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables>

Internal Project Management Link ... <https://github.com/multixscale/planning/issues/87>

thomas.roblitz@uib.no ... <mailto:thomas.roblitz@uib.no>

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0> ... <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

Page 1

Clowder framework ... <https://clowderframework.org>

CSCS ... <https://www.cscs.ch>

Cineca ... <https://www.cineca.it/en>

Page 3

Magic Castle ... https://github.com/ComputeCanada/magic_castle/tree/main/docs#magic-castle-documentation

Magic Castle ... https://github.com/ComputeCanada/magic_castle/tree/main/docs#magic-castle-documentation

detailed documentation is available in the Magic Castle GitHub repository ... https://github.com/ComputeCanada/magic_castle/tree/main/docs

Page 4

Puppet ... <https://www.puppet.com/>

Puppet Magic Castle ... https://github.com/ComputeCanada/puppet-magic_castle

Puppet Magic Castle ... https://github.com/ComputeCanada/puppet-magic_castle

Page 6

Lhumos GitHub repository ... https://github.com/Lhumos-dev/clowder_react_tf

Docker Compose ... <https://docs.docker.com/compose/>

extractors subfolder of the Lhumos repository ... https://github.com/Lhumos-dev/clowder_react_tf/tree/main/extractors

commit history of the Lhumos GitHub repository ... https://github.com/Lhumos-dev/clowder_react_tf/commits/main/

gitlab.com ... <https://gitlab.com/>

Page 8

Ambassador-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si ... Ambassador-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si

High-Performance Computing in Europe portal ... <https://hpc-portal.eu/>

FocusCoE ... <https://www.hpcwire.com/off-the-wire/focuscoe-successfully-completes-project-activities>

CASTIEL2 and the NCCs ... <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/services/training/>

by MultiXscale itself ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/all-eurohpc-training-events/>

training calendar tools are hosted on GitLab ... <https://gitlab.com/eurohpc/hpc-coe-calendars>

MultiXscale event history ... [https://hpc-portal.eu/past-events-courses/?field_efp_projects_value\[\]=multixscale](https://hpc-portal.eu/past-events-courses/?field_efp_projects_value[]=multixscale)

Page 9

SC23 to co-present a tutorial on Magic Castle with the lead developer ... <https://sc23.conference-program.com/presentation/?id=tut130&sess=sess216>

Citations

- [1] A. O’Cais, “D6.1 - guidelines for community outreach, education, and training,” Jan. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451845>